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Deliverable title: Proceedings of the workshop on Evolution of austenitic stainless steels and of protective coatings under irradiation

Work Package	Deliverable number	Lead contractor	Date
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	30/11/2021	23/11/2021	R
Description of the activities: Workshop on Ion and Neutron Irradiation of Nuclear Materials			
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1. Workshop on Ion and Neutron Irradiation of Nuclear Materials

In the framework of GEMMA's work package 3, it was organized the workshop: "Ion and Neutron Irradiation of Nuclear Materials", the program of which is copied in the following pages.

The goal of the workshop was to bring together the European and US scientific communities to discuss the present status of understanding the relationship between ion and neutron irradiation, from both a theoretical and experimental point of view. This is a crucial point for any future development of nuclear technology as a whole. In fact, materials qualification under a relevant neutron spectrum is a lengthy and costly process which inevitably leads to tens of years of research and costs in the range of millions of euros/dollars. Nowadays, this became an even more daunting issue, since there is no facility in the EU or US suitable to test materials under a fast fission spectrum, not to say a fusion one.

This typical egg and chicken problem requires the construction of dedicated irradiation facilities, which requires large amounts of public money and years to complete. Ion irradiation can bridge the gap between the present situation and when large experimental facilities will be available. In fact, ions facilities are already widely available and with ions only few days are necessary to reproduce the dose level experienced by a component in a nuclear reactor in its entire operational life. Moreover, generally with ions no activation occurs and materials characterization is simple and straightforward. Nevertheless, ions have specific drawbacks which limit their application as a mean to simulate ion irradiation.

The most noteworthy of these are:

- limited volume of irradiation (typically in the microns range);
- dose rates several orders of magnitude higher than with neutrons;
- significant electromagnetic interaction between the incoming ion and the material to be irradiated, especially relevant in the case of ceramics;
- experimental details like point beam with raster vs defocused beam and others.
- in situ vs ex situ irradiation.

Indeed, even if an irradiation standard exists, namely ASTM E521 – 96, still a full agreement in the scientific community on the best conditions to simulate neutron damage with ions is yet to come. The present workshop, brought together the best EU and US experts in the field from leading institutions like SCK-CEN, CEA, U. of Huddersfield, MIT, ORNL, INL, U. of

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Tennessee, ANL, IIT, U. of Manchester, to name a few. Different aspects of the ions vs neutron irradiation were discussed in the relevant cases of metals, mainly steels, and ceramics, mainly oxides, relevant in the field of nuclear reactors.

A general agreement on the constraints and limitations, yet of the great advantages of ion irradiation was achieved. It was stressed like it is of the utmost importance to adhere to the established guidelines for irradiating different materials and to extend the relationship between ion and neutron irradiation with further experimental and modelling tools. A special place is covered by in situ TEM irradiations which allow in a unique way, to acquire relevant kinetic data continuously following any phenomenon from the start up to damage levels as high as several tens of dpas.

It was decided this to be the first of a kind workshop which will be further extended to Asiatic institutions in the future.

All presentations and video recordings will be available for download at the following link:

http://www.eera-jpnm.eu/gemma/filesharer/documents/Meetings/2021_11_22-23_Workshop_Ion_and_neutron_irradiation_of_nuclear_materials/

ION AND NEUTRON IRRADIATION OF NUCLEAR MATERIALS

A GEMMA PROJECT WORKSHOP

22 November 2021 [2:00 p.m. - 6:15 p.m (CET)]

23 November 2021 [2:00 p.m. - 6:15 p.m (CET)]

To participate click on this Teams link: <http://bitly.ws/jDXA>

DAY 1

- 14:00** **Pietro Agostini, Fabio Di Fonzo**
The GEMMA project and the role of ion irradiation
- 14:15** **Steven Zinkle**
Leveraging the complementarity of ion and neutron irradiations for enhanced understanding of radiation effects.
- 15:00** **Maylise Nastar**
Modeling of radiation-induced segregation and phase transformation in model alloys of ferritic and austenitic steels
- 15:30** **Tonci Tadic**
Development of DiFU dual-beam facility for ion irradiation of nuclear materials at RBI, Zagreb

16:00 BREAK

- 16:15** **Boris Paladino**
Heavy Ion Irradiation of materials for lead fast reactor
- 16:45** **Łukasz Kurpaska**
Effects of radiation and temperature on the performance of PLD-grown alumina coatings
- 17:15** **Wei-Ying Chen**
In-situ krypton and helium dual beam irradiation in nickel
- 17:45** **Philipp Frankel**
MIDAS: Understanding irradiation damage in Zr alloys using Neutron and Ion irradiation

18:15 END OF DAY 1

ION AND NEUTRON IRRADIATION OF NUCLEAR MATERIALS

A GEMMA PROJECT WORKSHOP

DAY 2

14:00 William John Weber
Effects of Electronic Energy Loss on Damage Production &
Evolution in Ceramics

14:45 Davide Loiacono
In-situ heavy ion irradiation of amorphous ceramic

15:15 He Lingfeng
Dislocation loops in UO₂ and its surrogates

15:45 BREAK

16:00 Vladimir Vishnyakov
Properties of Cr₂AlC phases – towards nuclear applications

16:30 Michael Short
Revealing the hidden defects in neutron irradiated titanium
using stored energy

17:15 Konstantza Lambrinou
Radiation response of MAX phase ceramics

18:00 Round table and discussion

18:15 END OF DAY 2

